

EasyUnicode ReadMe v.5

EasyUnicode is a Keyboard layout file for Mac OS X (10.2 or later) to type Unicode characters for basic Sanskrit/Pali transcription. Key mapping is as follows:

ā: Opt+a	Ā: Opt+Shift+a
ī: Opt+i	Ī: Opt+Shift+i
ū: Opt+u	Ū: Opt+Shift+u
ṛ: Opt+r	Ṛ: Opt+Shift+r
ṙ: Opt+f	Ṙ: Opt+Shift+f
ḷ: Opt+l	Ḭ: Opt+Shift+l
ṅ: Opt+k or g	Ṅ: Opt+Shift+k or g
ṇ: Opt+c or j	Ṇ: Opt+Shift+c or j
ṭ: Opt+t	Ṭ: Opt+Shift+t
ḍ: Opt+d	Ḍ: Opt+Shift+d
ṇ: Opt+n	Ṇ: Opt+Shift+n
ś: Opt+s	Ś: Opt+Shift+s
ṣ: Opt+x	Ṣ: Opt+Shift+x
ḥ: Opt+h	Ḥ: Opt+Shift+h
ṁ: Opt+m	Ṃ: Opt+Shift+m

For other diacritical marks, see attached file "MappingChart." From EasyUnicode5 French and German special characters become easily accessible with "Option and Control" combination.

Instructions for installing

Download the file and you'll find a keyboard layout file for Unicode inputting named "EasyUnicode.keylayout." If you are using the previous version(s) of EasyUnicode, you should remove it from "Keyboard Layouts" folder before installation.

Now, you simply drag the "EasyUnicode.keylayout" file into the "Keyboard Layouts" folder in your "Library", or the top-level Library if you have admin privileges. The keyboard is immediately available to all applications that launch after this point; you have to quit and relaunch running applications (including the Finder) for them to recognize the keyboard. This includes System Preferences, which is the application that you use to add the keyboard to the keyboard menu. When in doubt, log out and in again.

Then, in order to add the EasyUnicode to your keyboard menu, choose it from either System Preference (language->input menu) or Menu-bar of the Finder.

The EasyUnicode is compatible with Mac OSX 10.7 Lion. However, Mac OS X 10.7 Lion hides user's ~/Library directory by default. If you want to access it, holding down the Option key will show the user's "Library" directory as an option in the Go menu in Menu-bar of the Finder.

Attached ".icns" file is a menubar icon. The icon will appear on Menu-bar when you put it in the "Keyboard Layouts" folder with ".keylayout" file.

From this version, EasyUnicode(R) comes with EasyUnicode. The difference is only that the Script assignment of the former is Roman but the latter is assigned to Unicode Script. You can install either or both of them.

If your hardware keyboard has any RomanScript-key like *Eisū*-key in the JIS (Japanese) keyboard, EasyUnicode(R) allows easier script switching.

As to Unicode font for Sanskrit/Pali transcription, you may use Times, Palatino, Lucida Grande or other fonts included in Mac OSX software. Many other good fonts such as [Gandhari Unicode font](#) and [Gentium](#) are elsewhere available. Please visit University of Washington Early Buddhist Manuscripts Project web-page ([Fonts](#)) for the Gandhari Unicode font and related information. The EasyUnicode will be uploaded on the same page when updated.

The EasyUnicode was generated through Alex Eulenberg's very useful page "[Unicode Keyboards for Mac](#)". It's all due to this page I could make the EasyUnicode.

This version of EasyUnicode is modified with [Ukelele](#), a very useful Unicode Keyboard Layout Editor written by John Brownie of SIL.

The Icon is based on the "Simple Button" icons created by Pedro Hernández, [elpincho Designs](#).

If you have any question, comment, or suggestion, you can contact me at:
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2011.8.6

Update Info.

η (Option and Control+n) added. It should be useful for the online version of [The Pali Text Society's Pali-English dictionary](#).

2011.6.4

Modifications:

In order to improve the accessibility of French and German special characters, "Option and Control" and "Option and Control+Shift" modifier sets are added.

Metrical symbols and upper *h* are included.

Most of "Unicode Combining Diacritical Marks" (0301-0362) are included.

For details, please see the attached file "MappingChart."

EasyUnicode(R) is packaged together.
ReadMe file and Mapping Chart are revised.
2011.4.6

Two major modifications:

"EasyUnicode-JIS.keylayout" is integrated in the "EasyUnicode.keylayout" This version is compatible with both ANJI and JIS (and probably with ISO, though unchecked) keyboards.

Unicode Combining Diacritical Marks (0301-0361) become accessible by pressing Opt+1. For example, you can combine acute accent mark "´" on any letter by typing "opt+1" and "e" after typing the letter to which you wish to add the accent mark. For details, please see the attached file "MappingChart."

ReadMe file revised.

2005.8.23

ž, Ž (opt+z, option+shift+z) added. ReadMe file revised.

I thank Ulrich Pagel for his valuable comment.

2005.1.19

File format is changed to XML format (".keylayout" file) from ".rsrc" file. Icon (".icns" file) added.

I appreciate Pedro Hernández, elpincho Designs for permitting me to use his beautiful icons. õ, Õ (opt+o, option+shift+o) added.

2005.1.11

Script assignment is corrected. It now become compatible with Microsoft Word (2004 version or later) and other Unicode managing applications.

Many thanks to Mark Blum for his useful comment!

2004.10.13

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